

Revue D'Études en Management et Finance D'Organisation N°14 Mars 2022

**IMPACT STUDY OF QUALITY CERTIFICATION ON ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE
ACCORDING TO THE MCKINSEY 7S MODEL: CASE OF SMES IN THE RABAT-SALÉ-
KÉNITRA REGION**

**ETUDE D'IMPACT DE LA CERTIFICATION QUALITÉ SUR LE CHANGEMENT
ORGANISATIONNEL SELON LE MODÈLE MCKINSEY 7S : CAS DES PME DE LA
RÉGION DE RABAT-SALÉ-KÉNITRA**

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Abstract

SMEs engage more in the way of business certification. However, few studies have been conducted on the possible implications of the certification process quality management system for SMEs in general and its organizational architecture in particular. The objective of this research is to analyze the impact of a management model of the structure of SMEs, according to a qualitative approach; so, it is to study the certification process in its relationship with organizational change compared with the McKinsey 7 S Model. In this article, we will present the results of empirical research that has been conducted on the process of quality certification (ISO 9000) in 30 SMEs in Rabat-Salé-Kénitra region certified by the Moroccan Standards Institute (IMANOR). The study leads to highlight a variety of perceptions of the quality approach that coexist in these companies, as well as varying degrees of involvement of members of the organization. It also shows that despite the process of adapting the certification process context, it sometimes involves an unfavorable change in these companies.

Keywords: Quality certification, Organizational change, Mckinsey 7S model

Résumé

Les PME s'engagent davantage dans la voie de la certification des entreprises. Cependant, peu d'études ont été menées sur les implications possibles du système de management de la qualité du processus de certification pour les PME en général et son architecture organisationnelle en particulier. L'objectif de cette recherche est d'analyser l'impact d'un modèle de gestion de la structure des PME, selon une approche qualitative ; il s'agit donc d'étudier le processus de certification dans sa relation avec le changement organisationnel par rapport au modèle 7S de McKinsey. Dans cet article, nous présenterons les résultats de recherches empiriques qui ont été menées sur le processus de certification qualité (ISO 9000) dans 30 PME de la région de Rabat-Salé-Kénitra certifiées par l'Institut marocain de normalisation (IMANOR). L'étude conduit à mettre en évidence une variété de perceptions de la démarche qualité qui coexistent dans ces entreprises, ainsi que divers degrés d'implication des membres de l'organisation. Il montre également que malgré le processus d'adaptation du contexte du processus de certification, il implique parfois un changement défavorable dans ces entreprises.

Mots clés : Certification de qualité, changement organisationnel, modèle 7S de McKinsey

Introduction

According to (M. Weill, 2001), the Second World War can be considered as a pivotal step in the transition to quality assurance. In modern economies where information flows and competition becomes stronger, more global, faster and more complex, no entrepreneur and no business can consider themselves immune to competitive play and out of the demands of competitiveness. In this new context, the emphasis is placed on the quality of the products because it is often seen as an essential performance criterion today (A.Guilhon & M.Weill). For this, certification to ISO 9000 standards seeks to provide companies with punctual recognition of the level of their management system, while ensuring quality over time since they are subject to regular external audits. Even in sectors where these standards are not demanded by customers, more and more companies are adopting the ISO 9000 system to differentiate themselves from the competition, to improve their image or even their competitiveness. The quality action therefore becomes a strategy and marketing tool allowing to have an advantage and an additional commercial argument compared to the competitors.

At the national level, in fact, the external pressures for certification are low: the clientele and the competition are still little aware of the certification arguments. Thus, the types and implications of these approaches in Moroccan SMEs in Rabat-Salé-Kénitra region certified for quality have not yet been studied in this sense. This observation led us to question the existence of an impact of the quality approach on the organization in general, the working methods, the predominant management style of these companies, and that this certification process implies a change as some authors suggest (Boronat & Canard, 1995). The question then arises: Does the commitment of SMEs in a quality certification process imply a favorable organizational change?

In this study, we will study the relationship between the quality certification process and organizational change. So, this approach requires a change in which component of the SME? Is this change favorable or unfavorable?

- H.1. Quality certification process and organizational change of the physical component;
- H.2. Quality certification process and organizational change of strategy;
- H.3. Quality certification process and organizational change of the structure;
- H.4. Quality certification process and organizational change of the system;
- H.5. Quality certification process and organizational change of the human component;
- H.6. Quality certification process and organizational style change.

1. LITERATURE ON THE QUALITY CERTIFICATION PROCESS

(J.M. Monin, 2001) asserts that, faced with the need to ensure trust between more and more actors, constantly renewed and independent, the quality assurance logic has gradually imposed itself, first through supplier approvals based on audits, then through third-party certification carried out on the basis of a common reference: ISO 9000 standards or sector equivalents.

1.1. Classical approach based on procedures : analytical modeling

Furthermore, for (D. Boeri' 2001), it is no longer a question of ensuring and measuring the quality of the product and service delivered, but of examining the body of procedures used to guarantee it. This author claims that procedural controls, internal or external, give new vigor to former Taylorians. "Quality assurance" ensures, as its name suggests, compliance with procedures and product / service compliance. Furthermore, according to (Y.F. Livian' 2001), the search for certification requires an analysis, then a written formalization of the operations. It's about making sure everything is done properly, competently and truthfully. So, there is a certain chapter of the standard corresponding to a written procedure request.

(J.L. Lemoigne, 1995) explains the analytical modeling of complicated systems by the use of a disjunctive logic that we now call formal logic. Indeed, for autor, the analytical method needs a disjunctive logic since the results of the division must be definitively distinguished and separated. Furthermore, (Y. Bertrand & P. Guillement' 1989) consider that analytical modeling is very useful when the number of elements in a system is very low. It then becomes easy to isolate a variable and analyze the behavior of the system. Furthermore, for (F. Lacroux, 1999), in the analytical approach, we postulate that it is possible to understand a phenomenon "by itself", "in isolation".

This is how we consider that the classic approach to the procedure-based certification approach corresponds very well to analytical modeling, since in this case, certification according to Y.F. Livian will lead to very "classic" analyzes and actions: Defining functions, improving coordination procedures, simplifying information circuits, etc. This corresponds to the Taylorian and Fayollian project. This idea was also justified by (F. Blanchot, H. Isaac and all.) who emphasize that at the same time, this method is based on the development of written procedures which each agent must respect. One would think then that it is only a return to a revisited form of industrial bureaucracy described by Mintzberg.

According to D. Boeri, in parallel with the development of certification, a certain number of criticisms were nonetheless voiced against ISO 9000 standards. Indeed, given their too great a number, standards become complex, too, the orientation of certification is essentially

"industrial" and does not guarantee the quality of products and services, since the basis of the benchmark is the only compliance with resource requirements (a company could produce bad products while meeting ISO 9000 requirements). Also, certification was a source of rigidity for the company, which froze its operation in a straitjacket, weighing down its meticulous control practices and unnecessary formalism. Thus, according to Y.F. Livian, Certification is experienced as a purely commercial constraint, which relaxes after obtaining the certificate, pending the auditor's inspection visit. Its organizational effects are often, in these cases, quite limited, since the analysis of activities and procedures is superficial and ownership remains weak. In addition, for (C. Dubernet & C. Marquette, 1998), the writing of work procedures, prior to any ISO 9000 certification, is generally carried out by function managers and by middle management. It is therefore an approach that can prove not very participative. Finally, these authors conclude that this approach is limited in this case to strict quality assurance without triggering continuous improvement.

1.2. Towards a new process-based approach : systemic modeling

- **From a production cycle logic to a process logic**

According to J.M. Monin, the authors of the 2000 revision of quality standards chose to orient the standard in a process logic. This development is first of all in the very structure of the standard which goes from a list of twenty thematic requirements to a system of four major macro processes: the piloting process; the resource management process; the production process; and the monitoring and improvement process. In the same vein, M. Weill stresses that this international standard encourages the adoption of a process approach when developing, implementing and improving the effectiveness of a quality management system, in order to increase customer satisfaction by meeting their requirements. Finally, F. Tessier considers that the version of the ISO 9001-2000 standard brings a new vision of quality, especially through the process approach, placing the customer at the center of its concerns. This new approach influences the organization of production units but especially that of the company: the objective is to move towards an increasingly transversal organization by involving all staff. It is therefore important: to understand and meet the requirements; to consider the processes in terms of added value; measure the performance and effectiveness of the processes; and continuously improve processes based on objective metrics. In short, several authors explain the process approach by using the model plotted in the diagram below, as well as the relationships between the processes described in articles 4 and 8 of ISO 9001-2000. This model covers all the requirements of this international standard, but does not present the processes at a detailed level.

Diagram N°1: Model of the process approach

Source: (M. Weill, 2001)

- **From mastery to continuous improvement**

According to J.M. Monin, the new standard clarifies and reinforces the requirements relating to permanent improvement mechanisms: listening to customers; measuring devices; the missions of the quality manager; the subject of the management review; the quality audit system ...

- **Simplicity**

According to J.M. Monin, today there is only one certification standard / ISO 9001 to replace (ISO 9001; ISO 9002; ISO 9003) with the choice of a simpler plan and consistent with the other standards. With this simplification, all the requirements will have to apply to the entire certified activity. None of the steps having an impact on quality can be excluded a priori from the scope of the new standard.

- **From compliance to satisfaction**

According to J.M. Monin, with the release of the 2000 version, the new standard requires the implementation of a real measure of customer satisfaction. We have thus moved from a logic of "quality compliance" to a more ambitious logic of "quality of satisfaction".

- **From requirements of means to requirements of principles**

The new version expresses requirements of principles, leaving more flexibility to the company for their modality and their degree of application. Indeed, only six written procedures remain imposed (control of documents; control of records relating to quality; control of non-

conformities; internal audit; corrective actions and preventive actions). For the rest, the company is only required to formalize the procedures and documents that it deems necessary for "effective operation and control of its processes".

Finally, J.L. Lemoigne emphasizes that the systemic approach consists in constructing representations or portraits that resemble reality. It makes it possible to produce models of organizational reality which are in no way irreducible to a finite model due to the complexity of the systems. Thus, according to (J. Soyer, 2000), to use a systemic approach is to take into account the fact that any modification of a sub-system will have effects on the others and it is therefore to plan all the adaptations which will contribute to the achievement of the objectives targeted.

The process-based approach corresponds very well to systemic modeling, because several authors insist on the idea that the process approach designates the application of a process system within an organism, as well as the identification, interactions and management of these processes. In addition, according to the new standard, "one of the advantages of the process approach is the permanent control which it allows over the relations between the processes within the process system, as well as over their combinations and interactions".

2. LITERATURE ON ORGANIZATIONAL CHANGE

(A. Guilhon, 1998) affirms that in the management sciences, the status of organizational change is not clear and ambivalent: it is radical or marginal, created by intentionality or by constraint, analyzed by its authors or its actors.

2.1. The classic approach

According to (V. Perret, 1998), the dilemma of organizational change often arises as the double constraint of its necessity and its great difficulty. This dilemma is part of the existence of an organizational duality between action and context. The classic resolutions of this dilemma translate into exclusive and opposite responses that focus either on the context to explain the difficulties and organizational inertia as defended by deterministic theories, or on action to explain change, as he proposes voluntarist theories.

2.1.1. The deterministic approach

(V. Perret, 1996) demonstrates that the deterministic conception of organizational change insists on the inflexible nature of the organization and sees in the structure, the system, the culture of rigidity and inertia which tend to preserve the organization of changes. This deterministic conception emphasizes the factors of permanence of the organization and sees

environmental pressures (external factors) as the main driver of organizational transformations. This vision of organization gave birth to the work of theorists of natural selection (Aldrich) or to the theories of population ecology (Hannan & Freeman) who consider organizational dynamics essentially in the sense of an environmental action on the organization. This approach sees companies essentially as passive entities or rather reactive to environmental stimuli, the reactions being strongly structured by the environmental context.

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In addition, according to (A. Guilhon, 1998), the theories claiming to be from the school of determinism believe that the organization only adapts to external pressures. According to Katz & Kahn or Cyert & March, although the actors of the organization hold a central place in their theory, it is always the idea of adaptation and responses to external pressures that dominates the relationship between the organization and its environment. Conversely, theories of contingency (Mintzberg; Miller & Friesen) or of population ecology (Hannan & Freeman) give central weight to the environment which guides the structural organization of businesses. So, among determinists, it is mainly the ability to adapt that gives SMEs a new place in the theory of organizations.

2.1.2. The proactive approach

According to (I.V. DERUMEZ, 1998), the previous approaches, emphasizing the imposed character of organizational change, neglect two fundamental elements of the theory of organizations (Joffre & Koenig): reality cannot be considered as an independent datum, and the organization is not adapted to reality but to the perception of it by the actors. The choice to make a change or not becomes voluntary. Indeed, (A.L. Bassetti, 2002) affirms that for the proactive current, the change arises from a situation of stress and tension in the organization which takes shape in the inconsistency between three levels: structure, culture, and leadership, the context (Guilhon, 2001). It therefore appears from Child's proposals that two logical alternatives can characterize environmental voluntarism: voluntarism by the absence of constraints (anti-determinism) and voluntarism by a capacity for action and influence which we can call proactivity. Thus, for V. Perret, the proactive approach highlights the preponderant role of strategic choices, of the actor as a factor of transformation of the organization. In addition, organizational development theorists (Beckard; Beer), who represent the prevailing current in managerial literature on change, share and develop in their approaches this voluntarist and deliberate conception placing the leader at the center of the change process.

The theses of the enactment developed by Weick and the socio-cognitive current extend in an original way the voluntarist thought. The environment can be seen as an extension of the

organization where leaders will try to impose order. The context is no longer an objective, homogeneous and directly influencing factor. Each company will define its own context and adjust its actions accordingly in order to modify it. Smircich & Stubbart believe that the idea that organizations must adapt to their objective environment should be abandoned. The environment being directly derived from the organization, there is not a single type of environment which imposes its characteristics but a multiplicity of interpretation of the context.

2.2. THE PARADOXICAL APPROACH OF ORGANIZATIONS

According to V.Perret, the paradoxical approach of organizations invites us to no longer consider the two poles (deterministic and proactive) as antagonistic and mutually exclusive. The nature of the intentional action of change must take into account the reciprocal play of the two poles which are defined mutually by their constant interaction (Crozier & Freidberg; Giddens). This complex vision of the "Action-Context" relationship allows us to highlight the dual nature of action "on" a context and "in" a given organizational context. In order to allow change, the leader's action must seek to structure the organizational context with a view to transforming it, but it is, at the same time, structured by this context. A conceptualization of the dual nature of the activity of change was proposed in a previous work in the form of the "Demarcation / Support" model (Perret; Perret & Ramananstsoa). The logic of demarcation refers to the activity of the leader which aims to act on an organizational context that he seeks to transform. Support logic refers to the need for the leader to act according to an organizational context to which he must conform and adapt. This model highlights the fundamental ambivalence of the leader's action.

Thus, based on the works of Astley & V.D. Ven, Hrebiniack & Joyce consider that the two visions of the adaptation of the company are complementary, introducing a strong interactivity, an important relationship between the environment and decisions. The purpose is no longer to know which element is predominant but rather to reflect on the respective and mutual contributions of these two elements. The explanation of the organizational and strategic behavior of the company will depend on this interaction.

3. CONSTRUCTED RESEARCH PRACTICE

The SME in Morocco faces needs at the size of its challenges since it constitutes the economic mattress of the kingdom.

Table N°1 : The Moroccan SME in Figures

95% of Moroccan companies	50% of employment	20% of added value
30% of exports	40% of production	50% of investment

Source: OECD

According to the last published report of ISO Survey 2011, the number of Moroccan companies certified ISO 9001 is 261 certifications in 2011, Morocco is in 6th position behind South Africa which recorded 3,409 certifications, Egypt with 2,076, Tunisia with 477, Kenya with 278 and finally Algeria with 268 certifications in the same year.

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A. Guilhon asserts that SMEs can, independently of a client, be engaged in strategic quality processes because the manager perceives a need or plans an expansion strategy centered on an image of quality, even total quality. For him, quality constitutes for SMEs a means of creating a competitive advantage centered on cost control and reduction of cost inefficiencies or on an image of differentiation acquired by mastering production and information processes, aiming to offer products that respond to changes in demand. It is therefore assumed that the quality certification process implies a favorable organizational change in the SME.

On the basis of this hypothesis, the explanatory variable (X) is "the quality certification process", and the variable to be explained (Y) is "favorable organizational change". The relationship between these two variables allows us to build the synthetic and hypothetical model of this research.

McKinsey developed following the work of four authors a methodology: the so-called 7S method. The original authors (Richard Pascale, Anthony Athos, Tom Peters and Robert Waterman) of this method started from their results on efficient and effective companies to determine seven criteria which help to make a business run smoothly. The diagram below clearly shows the correspondence between the seven key success factors of an organization according to the McKinsey model and the sorted elements of quality management under the ISO standards:

Table N°2: Management building blocks

		Reference models	
		ISO 9000	McKinsey 7 S
Building blocks	Strategy Value & Development	Management responsibility	Strategy
	Structure Processes & Organization	Quality Management System	Structure
	Culture Leadership & Core values	Management responsibility	Style, Shared values
	People Competence development	Resource management	Staff, Skills
	Resources ICT, Money facilities	Resource management	Systems

	Results Products & Effects	Monitoring Analysis Customer satisfaction	-
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Source: (Nieuwenhuis, 2003-2006)

From this board, we can highlight the variables constituting our research model.

Xi	Explanatory variables (from ISO 9000 standard)
X1	Liability of managers (management commitment; quality policy; planning; responsibility; authority and communication; general review of the system; etc.)
X2	Resource management (human resources and infrastructure: skills, training, work environment, etc.)
X3	Quality management system (documentary requirements; quality manual; etc.)
X4	Product realization (product requirements; communication with customers; design and development; production control; etc.)
X5	Measurement, analysis and improvement (assessment of customer satisfaction; control of non-conformities; continuous improvement; preventive and corrective actions; etc.)

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Yi	Variables to explain (from the 7 S model “McKinsey model)
Y1	Change in the human component
Y2	Change in physical component
Y3	Change in structure
Y4	Change of the organization management system
Y5	Change in strategy

To study the impact of the explanatory variables on the variables to be explained, field surveys were used for companies located in Rabat, and others by telephone and email for the rest of the sample located in the others. cities in the Rabat-Salé-Kénitra region. To do this, we used a questionnaire composed of: closed questions with only one possible answer; questions closed to several answers; closed questions with ranking; semi-open questions; and open questions. The results of our empirical study are presented in the following table:

Table N°3: Presentation of the results

Elements of the ISO standard	McKinsey 7S Variables	Observations and conclusions	Impact of the ISO standard on organizational change
Human component	Staff / Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of adaptation to new situations ➔ Acceptance of the change, but with great difficulty for most of the staff • Development of training programs deemed very useful and more effective after engagement 	Adverse impact in general, given the difficulties encountered in adapting to change. This shows us that in the long term, staff may not be able to resist the change in their organization

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➔ The evaluation of the training effectiveness and actions of personnel required by the standard makes training much more effective • Evolution of the theoretical skills of the staff after the adoption of the standard • Practical skills of staff and learning in teams deemed sufficient by all companies 	
Physical component	Style / Shared values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of new installations and addition of workspace installations, etc. ➔ Development sense and Long-Term vision 	Favorable impact
Structure	Structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All companies define levels of responsibility after certification ➔ Vertical specialization of companies • The majority have a large number of different services after adopting the approach • Creation of a steering structure and appointment of a quality manager ➔ Functional specialization of companies • Majority of procedures used / Higher level of standardization ➔ Massive use of procedures • Frequent circulation of written information to replace the oral culture characterizing the period before engagement ➔ Strong formalization after the adoption of the standard 	Favorable impact
System	System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of formalized planning in the financial, production and marketing fields before the adoption of the quality approach, and also in the areas of training and quality management after the adoption of the standard ➔ Formalization of the planning system more important especially in the field of quality management and training after the adoption of the certification process • Exercise of controls through records to be filled in using computer process monitoring and measurement tables instead of controls based solely on monitoring information over time without recording before adopting the approach ➔ Formalization of the control system more important than before the engagement of the SME • Existence of a procedures manual, a written description of the workstations, a written statement of company policies, a quality manual and an organizational chart. However, before the adoption of the standard, companies only had manufacturers' manuals, evaluation sheets, anomaly sheets, productivity sheets, manufacturing sheets and account opening. ➔ Implementation of a more developed document system than before the adoption of the standard, therefore a more elaborate internal information system • Use of formalized internal communication after the adoption of the quality approach, therefore recourse to the written 	Favorable impact
Strategy	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better planning of the distribution of scarce resources to achieve the goals set with the adoption of the quality certification approach by all of the companies interviewed 	Favorable impact

Conclusion

The objective of this article was to study and analyze the impact of the quality certification process on the organizational change of SMEs in Rabat-Salé-Kenitra region, and to show in parallel if this impact is favorable for companies. We therefore conducted a survey of SMEs certified ISO 9000 by the Moroccan Institute for Standardization (IMANOR) by matching the variables determined in the ISO 9000 standard and the variables of the McKinsey model known as the 7S model. The results show that, in general, the commitment of all companies in a quality certification process has a favorable impact on organizational change, but have emphasized the most important point for the organizational development, that of the capacity of companies to resist the change of their organizations. It is therefore not enough to decree change for it to take place, but who says change says resistance. We are therefore moving towards the management of change, which stands out as a key concept, the aim of which is to lead a complete organization towards new objectives which will ensure the proper development of the organization.

- ✓ To what extent do these quality approaches meet resistance, or on the contrary a cooperation of the members of the organization?
- ✓ Can we draw conclusions about what to do for companies that will soon be certified?

We take up again the idea of the author V. Perret: If the change can be considered as object and source of paradox, it is that effectively it can only be conceived and constructed in a close relationship with its opposite: « **PERMANENCE** »

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